

SPEAKING OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8179169>

Fayzieva Gulzoda Ulugbekovna

5th year student of the Faculty of Practical Psychology

Tashkent State Pedagogical University

Laureate of scholarship named after Navoi

Annotation.

In this work, a retrospective analysis of the problem of the study of emotional intelligence has been carried out. Based on the review of sources, it is concluded that the interest in the emotional sphere of the person was already typical for the thinkers of antiquity, who at that time debated about the ratio of affective and rational in the person. The views of ancient philosophers on the nature of emotions had a significant impact on the ideas of scientists of subsequent eras. An analysis of the preconditions for the emergence of the term "emotional intelligence" and the reasons for its rapid spread has been made. The terms are similar to those used by various authors, whose work highlights various aspects of the problem. The essence of emotional intelligence has been clarified, its contents have been revealed, and the most well-known definitions are presented.

Keywords

emotions, thinking, emotional intelligence, emotional sphere, emotional states, emotional manifestations, emotional intelligence dimension, emotional coefficient (E), activity, motivation, self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, emotional management, educational programs for the development of emotional intelligence.

Emotional intelligence, like psychology in general, has a long backstory, but a short story. Philosophical prerequisites of scientific ideas about emotional intelligence were laid in the ancient period: for example, Plato was convinced that in the emotional life of people necessarily the presence of rationality; Aristotle insisted on the need to keep negative emotions (fear and anger) under special control of the mind. In the Middle Ages, scholastics adhered to the principle of the connection of thinking and feeling. The views of ancient thinkers had a significant influence on the philosophical ideas of the Enlightenment: the ancestor of rationalism R. Descartes saw in emotions a special type of passion; The Scottish philosopher D. Yum allowed the influence of emotions on the part of thinking that is connected with self-consciousness; Dutch philosopher B. Spinoso considered

affectes as motives for actions. One of the greatest thinkers of the 18th century, J.-J. Rousseau reflected on the role of emotions in education: the philosopher argued that learning would be difficult if it was based solely on logical postulates, for in the matter of cognition a person follows emotions. In 1872, in his book "Expression of Emotions in Humans and Animals," Darwin argued that evolutionary development and change occurs not only on a biological, but also on a mental, behavioral level. There was an evolutionary theory of emotions, in which the biological nature and benefits of emotions were explained as an important adaptive mechanism that contributes to the body's adaptation to the environment.

The introduction of the term "emotional intelligence" into scientific use was preceded by a gradual change in the point of view on the ratio of emotional and cognitive processes. At the beginning of the 20th century, the German psychologist G. Maier in his book "The Psychology of Emotional Thinking" proposed a classification of types of thinking: in addition to logical, he singled out and emotional; in turn, the emotional delineated to affective (religious and aesthetic) and willful. In the 1940s, the American psychologist D.Wechsler wrote about the existence of emotional abilities in the publication "Unintellectual Factors in General Intelligence." In the late 1940s, the American explorer R.W.Leeper suggested the idea of emotional thinking.

Following the requirements of the time, in 1985, clinical physiologist and psychologist R.Bar-On, rethinking already prepared theories about the place of emotions and intelligence in the structure of personality, for the first time will introduce the term E (Emotional quotient), a factor emotionality, similar to the I.I., and will suggest that the E.E. reliably predicts the success of people and in the future will completely replace the measurement of intelligence in education, in the diagnosis and correction of psychopathology, in employment, training and certification Staff. Following him, W.L. Payne publishes materials about the types and forms of intelligence, where among other forms mentions the emotional.

The introduction of the term "emotional intelligence" into scientific circulation takes place in 1990, which is facilitated by American psychologists J. Meyer (J.Mayer) and P.Salovey. They proposed a model of the structure of emotional intelligence, defining it as a model of ability. According to this model, the structure of emotional intelligence includes three types of abilities, each of which has certain components:

- the ability to identify and express emotions (the ability to identify and express one's emotions, the ability to identify and express other people's emotions);

- ability to regulate emotions (ability to regulate their emotions, ability to regulate other people's emotions);

- the ability to use emotions in thinking and activity (the ability to flexible planning, redirected attention, creative thinking, motivation).

In addition, U.S. researchers have detailed the method of measuring emotional intelligence [1].

Another attempt to structure the phenomenon of emotional intelligence is the D.Goleman model. In his opinion, the components of emotional intelligence are: self-awareness is the ability to adequately assess one's strength and abilities; self-regulation - the ability to control emotions, so that they do not interfere with the current work; Motivation is the ability to use deep inclinations and preferences to achieve a goal; empathy is the ability to understand what other people are experiencing, the ability to put themselves in their place; social skills - the ability to read emotions in the relationship between other people [2].

D. Goelman and his followers have repeatedly stated that the possession of emotional intelligence allows a person to be successful in different fields of activity.

Later, the model of emotional intelligence was refined to reflect new knowledge and, at present, it includes four components: the identification of emotions - the ability to identify, adequately express and perceive emotions; use of emotions to improve the efficiency of thinking and activity - the ability to use your emotions to focus attention on the most important events, the ability to evoke certain emotions necessary to improve efficiency Activities, the ability to use different sides of the mood to analyze different points of view on the problem being solved; understanding of emotions - the ability to understand different emotions, connections between emotions, transitions, causes; Emotion management - the ability to control emotions, and be able to choose emotions depending on the situation [1].

The clarification of the essence of emotional intelligence takes place closer to the turn of millennia and in the first decades of the new century, when there is an abundance of publications on the subject. In various sources it can be seen that along with the term "emotional intelligence" used such concepts as emotional potential, emotional thinking, emotional consciousness, emotional competence, emotional competence, emotional Sensitivity [3, p. 71].

In Russian psychology, G.G. Garskov used the term "emotional intelligence" first. The author connects emotional intelligence with the ability to understand the personality through emotional manifestations, so that "to manage the emotional sphere on the basis of intellectual analysis and synthesis" [4, p. 25]. In 2001, the St.

Petersburg publishing house published E.P. Ilyin's textbook Emotions and Feelings. After analyzing the definitions formulated in foreign sources, the author of the book proposes the most general formulation of emotional intelligence: it is "emotional-intellectual activity" [5, p. 243].

In 2004, the collective work "Social Intelligence" was published. One of the chapters of the work, written by D.V. Lucin, O.O. Maryutin and A.S. Stepanov, is devoted to emotional intelligence. The definition is revealed as follows: it is "the ability to understand and control others' emotions" [6, p. 129].

Here are a few more definitions of emotional intelligence from the works of the past few years:

- it is an "integral category in the structure of the intellectual and emotional-willed sphere of the individual" that determines the success of its activities and relationships with others [7, p 11];

- it is an "integrative education that provides awareness, understanding and regulation of others' own emotions and emotions" and enables successful interpersonal interaction [8, p. 10];

- it is an "internal emotional resource of human emotional regulation" that allows the subject to control his behavior, keep emotions under control in problematic situations and achieve economic well-being [9, p. 7].

Thus, despite the difference in definitions, in the most general form emotional intelligence can be linked to the ability of the individual to interpret emotions - their own and other people's, on the basis of which to organize effective interaction in Society.

Speaking of emotional intelligence, it is worth noting that among the researchers of this problem there is no unity of opinion as to what advantages a person who has such a type of intellect can have.

According to D. Goulman, such people are socially active and their activities are productive; They are successful. their lives are full of events; they are not preoccupied with disturbing reflections; contact with others, they adhere to ethical principles [2, p. 79]. Those who have insufficient emotional intelligence are prone to mood swings, which ultimately has an impact on productivity [2, p. 64]. Russian researcher I.N. Andreeva believes that the presence of emotional intelligence allows the personality to be more adaptive to changes in society due to the ability to control internal impulses [10, p. 42].

However, American psychologists S. Anderson (S.Anderson), J. J.V.Ciarrochi, F.P.Dean, hold the belief that the presence of a highly developed ability to interpret the emotions of others, as well as increased sensitivity to positive, as well as

negative emotional depression [11]. Therefore, low emotional sensitivity has its advantages.

Despite the existing disagreements on this issue, the authors of most studies believe that the ability to manage emotions is a prerequisite for successful integration into society. This means that it is vital to develop the appropriate skill. The best period for the development of emotional intelligence is childhood, as indicated by the materials of a large number of studies. It is noted that the ability to recognize and manage one's feelings forms a way of behavior that becomes a human-to-need. In other words, it is a habit, and it can become vitally defining. [12, p. 99].

The development of emotional intelligence should cover all levels of human activity - the planning of interaction, the choice of interlocutors for communication, the nature of interaction. Many programs developed by scientific teams are freely available (on the Internet), which allows them to be used for distance education. Programs aimed at developing the emotional intelligence of students within the framework of inclusive education have become known

REFERENCES:

1. Dobrin A.V. The theoretical basis of the study of emotional intelligence and its relationship with psychological and psychophysiological parameters / A.V. Dobrin // Psychology of education in multicultural space. Scientific journal. - Yelets, 2013. - Tome 1. - No.21. - P. 5-10.
2. Goulman D. Emotional Intelligence / J. Goulman; Lane. With ang. A.P. Isaeva. - M.: AST MOSCOW; Vladimir: WCT, 2009. - 478 p.
3. Alexandrova N.P. To the question of the essence of the concept of "emotional intelligence" / N.P. Alexandrova // Herald RUDN. Series: Psychology and pedagogy. - 2009. No 1. p. 71 - 75.
4. Garskova G.G. Introduction of the concept of "emotional intelligence" to psychological theory / G.G. Garskova // Ananiev readings - 99: thesis. Scien. Pract.26-28 Oct. 1999/Under general. Red. A.A. Krylova; St. Petersburg: Izd-vo S.-Peterb. Un-ta, 1999. 25 - 26.
5. Ilyin E.P. Emotions and Feelings: Study. Allowance for the student. universities / E.P. Ilyin. St. Petersburg: Peter, 2001. - 752 s.
6. Social Intelligence: Theory, Measurement, Research / Under Ed. D.V. Lucina, D.V. Ushakova. - M.: In-t psychology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2004. - 176 s.

7. Davydova Y.V. Emotional Intelligence: Essential Signs, Structure and Features of Manifestation in Adolescence: Author's Diss. ... It's not a A psycho. Sciences / Y.V. Davydova. M., 2011. 22 s.

8. Meshcheryakova I.N. Development of emotional intelligence in students-psychologists in the process of studying at the university: author's dissertation. ... It's not a A psycho. Sciences / I.N. Meshcheryakova. Kursk, 2011. - 27 s.

9. Kiselyova T.S. Emotional intelligence as a vital resource and its development in adults: the author's dissertation. ... It's not a A psycho. Science / T.S. Kiselyova. M., 2015. - 26 s.

10. Andreeva I.N. Emotional intelligence as a phenomenon of modern psychology: monograph / I.N. Andreev. - Novopolotsk: PSU, 2011. - 388 s.

11. Ciarrochi J.V. Emotional intelligence moderates the relationship between stress and mental health / J.V. Ciarrochi, F.P. Dean, S. Anderson // Personality and Individual Differences. - 2002. V. 32. P. 197 - 209.

12. Szagvozdkin V.K. Emotional intelligence and its development in the conditions of family upbringing / V.K. Szagvozdkin // Cultural-historical psychology. - 2008. No 2. 97 - 103.